

KESIK PIRAMIDA TUSHUNCHASI. KESIK PIRAMIDANING YON SIRTINI TOPISH FORMULALARI.

Latipova Shahnoza Salim qizi

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti

“Umumtexnik fanlar” kafedراسi o’qituvchisi

slatipova543@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10652606>

Abstract

Language teaching and learning programs provide students the opportunity to discover how languages are learned and how they may be most-effectively taught. These programs allow students to consider questions including the subsequent: What theoretical troubles underline the teaching and studying of language?

Key words: language, learning, teaching, second language, communication, speech, human behavior, expression, synonyms of language. Getting to know a second language is a protracted and complicated venture. Your complete individual is affected as you conflict to attain past the confines of your first language and into a new language, a new lifestyle, a brand new way of questioning, feeling, and appearing. Overall commitment, general involvement, a complete physical, intellectual. And emotional reaction is essential to efficiently send and receive messages in a second language. Many variables are worried in the acquisition process. Language mastering isn't a fixed of smooth steps that can be programmed in a brief do-it-yourself package. So much is at stake that courses in overseas languages are often inadequate education grounds, in and of themselves, for the success learning of a 2d language. Few if any human beings achieve fluency in a foreign language solely inside the confines of the lecture room. It is able to seem contradictory, then, that this eBook is about both gaining knowledge of and coaching. however some of the contradiction is removed if you have a look at the coaching process as the facilitation of getting to know, wherein you may educate an overseas language correctly if, among other matters, you realize something approximately that tricky net of variables that are spun together to have an effect on how and why one learns or falls to research a 2d language.

LANGUAGE

Language is using a system of communicate which consists of a set of sounds or written symbols. College students tested how youngsters collect language. Language isn't artwork but each is styles of human conduct.

Synonyms: speech, communicate, expression, talking extra synonyms of language. Styles of language: Expressive language: How infants talk to others thru increasingly more sophisticated speech and improved vocabulary. Pragmatic language: all the subtle facets of language – facial expressions, body, moves, tone, extent, inflection, thoughts about whilst to speak and for how lengthy. This kind that helps you to examine. Due to the fact this is conversation of human beings. This is a vital part. A definition is a statement captures the important thing features of an idea. Those capabilities may additionally vary, relying for your own (or the lexicographer's) know-how of the construct. And, most crucial, that know-how is basically a "principle" that explicates the assemble. So a definition of a term can be notion of as a condensed version of a concept. Conversely, a concept is really—or now not so certainly—an extended definition. Defining, dicrefore is critical commercial enterprise: it calls for choices about which aspects of something are worthy of being included. Assume you were stopped by means of a reporter on the street, and inside the route of an interview about your field of examine, you have been requested: "nicely, because you're interested by second language acquisition, please define language in a sentence or two." you will absolute confidence dig deep into your reminiscence for a typical dictionary-kind definition of language. Such definitions, if pursued seriously, may want to lead to a lexicographer's wild-goose chase, however they can also mirror a fairly coherent synopsis of cutting-edge information of simply what its miles that linguists are seeking to study.

Gaining knowledge of AND teaching

We also can ask questions about constructs like getting to know and coaching. Recollect once more some conventional definitions. A seek in current dictionaries exhibits that getting to know is "acquiring or getting of understanding of a subject or a skill via look at, experience, or instruction." learning, and coaching of mastering, may be described as "showing or helping a person to learn how to do something, giving instructions, guiding inside the observe of something, supplying with information, causing to recognize or apprehend." isn't it curious that professional lexicographers seem to have such issue in devising a definition of something as prevalent as coaching? Extra than perhaps anything else, such definitions reflect the issue of defining complicated principles. Breaking down the components of the definition of learning, we can extract, as we did with language, domains of research and inquiry;

1. Learning is acquisition or "getting."
2. Studying is retention of records or skill.

3. Retention implies storage structures, reminiscence, and cognitive organization.
4. Getting to know includes lively, aware awareness on and performing upon activities outdoor or inside the organism.
5. Gaining knowledge of is especially permanent but issue to forgetting.
6. Mastering entails a few shape of practice, possibly reinforced practice.
7. Gaining knowledge of is a trade in behavior. Those principles can also supply manner to a number of subfields inside the area of psychology: acquisition procedures. Perception, memory (storage) systems, short- and lengthy-time period memory, take into account, motivation, aware and unconscious getting to know styles and techniques, theories of forgetting, reinforcement, the role of exercise. in no time the idea of gaining knowledge of will become every bit as complex because the concept of language. Yet the second language learner brings these types of (and greater) variables into play within the getting to know of a second language. Coaching can't be described aside from studying. Coaching is guiding and facilitating getting to know, enabling the learner to examine, placing the conditions for getting to know. Your understanding of ways the learner learns will decide your philosophy of training, your coaching style, your technique, methods, and classroom strategies. A idea of teaching, in concord together with your incorporated understanding of the learner and of the challenge remember to be found out, will factor the way to successful tactics on a given day for given newbies beneath the numerous constraints of the unique context of getting to know. In different phrases, your principle of teaching is your concept of mastering "stood on its head."

Conclusion

As you see, those types of strategies that could assist to study 2d language. Now, we discussed approximately them. We assume you may recognize this technique. Simplest your activities can't assist you, however also you must understand these kinds of techniques, techniques, elements. With one word gaining knowledge of 2d language this is difficult and smooth. It depends in your plan and activities. But you don't accept as true with any styles of methods, improvements. Because all of them that are not development. **ANNOTATSIYA.**

Piramida va uning elementlari haqida boshlangich ma'lumotlarni to'plash va o'rganish. 10-11 sinflarda geometriya fanini o'qitishda pedagogik texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanishni tashkil etish yo'llari keltirilgan.

“Kesik piramida va uning elementlari. Kesik piramidaning yon sirti” mavzusining kompetensiyaga asoslangan namunaviy dars ishlanmasi tayyorlash.

Kalit soʻzlar: Piramida, yon yoq, tekislik, tetraedr, koʻpburchak.

Piramida deb shunday koʻpyoqqa aytiladiki, u yassi koʻpburchak - piramida asosidan, asos tekisligida yotmagan nuqta - piramida uchidan va uchni asosining nuqtalari bilan tutashtiruvchi hamma kesmalardan iborat.

Piramidaning uchini asosining uchlari bilan tutashtiruvchi kesmalar Piramidaning yon qirralari deyiladi,

Piramidaning sirti asosidan va yon yoqlaridan iborat: Har bir yon yoq uchburchak. Uning uchlaridan biri Piramidaning uchi boʻladi, qarshisidagi tomoni esa piramida asosining tomoni boʻladi. Piramidaning uchidan asos tekisligiga tushirilgan perpendikulyar piramidaning balandligi deyiladi.

Piramidaning asosi n burchakdan iborat boʻlsa, u n burchakli piramida deyiladi. Uchburchakli piramida *tetraedr* deb ham ataladi.

rasmda tasvirlangan piramidaning asosi $A_1A_2...A_n$ koʻpburchak, piramidaning uchi S , yon qirralari $SA_1, SA_2, \dots, SA_n$, yon yoqlari $\triangle SA_1A_2, \triangle SA_2A_3, \dots$

Bundan keyin biz faqat asosida qavariq koʻpburchak boʻlgan piramidalarni qaraymiz. Bunday piramidalar qavariq koʻpyoqlar boʻladi.

Piramida va uning yassi kesimlarini yasash.

Parallel proeksiyalash qoidalariga muvofiq piramidaning tasviri quyidagi tarzda yasaladi. Avval asosi yasaladi. Bu biror yassi koʻpburchak boʻladi. Keyin piramidaning uchi belgilanadi, u yon qirralar yordamida asos uchlari bilan birlashtiriladi a)-rasmda besh burchakli piramidaning tasviri koʻrsatilgan.

Piramidaning uchi orqali oʻtuvchi tekisliklar bilan kesimlari uchburchaklardan iborat (a-rasm). Xususan, diagonal kesimlar uchburchaklar boʻladi. Bunday kesimlar piramidaning ikkita qoʻshni boʻlmagan yon qirralari orqali oʻtuvchi tekisliklar bilan xosil qilinadi (b-rasm).

Piramidaning asos tekisligidagi berilgan g izli tekislik bilan kesimi ham xuddi prizmaning kesimi kabi yasaladi. Piramidaning tekislik bilan kesimini yasash uchun uning yon yoqlarini kesuvchi tekislik bilan kesishmasini yasash yetarli.

Agar g izga parallel bo'lmagan yoqda kesimga tegishli bo'lgan biror A nuqta ma'lum bo'lsa, u xolda avval kesuvchi tekislikdagi g izning shu yoqning tekisligi bilan kesishmasi a - rasmdagi D nuqta yasaladi. D nuqta to'g'ri chiziqdagi A nuqta bilan tutashtiriladi. U xolda bu to'g'ri chiziqning yoqqa tegishli bo'lgan kesmasi bu yoqning kesuvchi tekislik bilan kesishmasidan iborat bo'ladi.

Agar A nuqta g izga parallel yoqda yotsa, u xolda kesuvchi tekislik bu

yoqni g to'g'ri chiziqqa parallel kesma bo'yicha kesib o'tadi. Qo'shni yon yoqda o'tib, uning kesuvni tekislik bilan kesishmasi yasaladi va hokazo. Natijada piramidaning talab etilayotgan kesimi xosil bo'ladi.

b – rasmda to'rtburchakli piramidaning asos tomoni va uning yon qirralaridan birida yotgan A nuqtadan o'tuvchi tekislik bilan kesimi yasaladi.

Kesik piramida

T e o r e m a. Piramidaning asosiga parallel va uni kesib o'tadigan tekislik shu piramidaga o'xshash piramida ajratadi.

Isboti. Faraz qilaylik, S - piramidaning uchi, A - asosining uchi, A' - kesuvchi tekislikning SA' yon qirra bilan kesishish nuqtasi (a- rasm). Piramidani S uchiga nisbatan gomotetiya koeffisienti bilan gomotetik almashtiramiz.

$$k = \frac{SA'}{SA}$$

Bunday gomotetiyada asos tekisligi A' nuqta orqali o'tuvchi parallel tekislikka o'tadi, ya'ni kesuvchi tekislikka o'tadi, demak, butun piramida bu tekislik kesib ajratgan qismga o'tadi. Piramidaning kesib ajratilgan qismi berilgan piramidaga o'xshash piramida bo'ladi. Teorema isbotlandi.

Teoreмага ko'ra piramida asosining tekisligiga parallel bo'lgan va piramidaning yon qirralarini kesib o'tuvchi tekislik piramidadan unga o'xshash piramida ajratadi. Ajratilgan bo'lakning ikkinchi qismi ham ko'pyok bo'lib, kesik piramida deb ataladi (b-rasm). Kesik piramidaning parallel tekisliklarda yotgan yoqlari piramidaning asoslari deyiladi qolgan yoqlari esa yon yoqlari deyiladi. Kesik piramidaning asoslari o'xshash (xatto gomotetik) uchburchaklardan, yon yoqlari esa trapesiyalardan iborat.

M a s a l a (1). Piramidaning yon qirradi to'rtta teng qismga ajratilgan va bo'linish nuqtalaridan asosiga parallel tekisliklar o'tkazilgan. Asosining yuzi 400 sm^2 ga teng. Kesimlarning yuzlarini toping.

Y e c h i l i s h i. Kesimlar piramidaning asosiga $\frac{1}{4}, \frac{2}{4}$ va $\frac{3}{4}$ o'xshashlik koeffisientlari bilan o'xshashdir.

O'xshash figuralarning yuzlari nisbati chiziqli ulchovlari kvadratlarining nisbati kabi bo'ladi. Shuning uchun kesimlar yuzlarining piramida asoslari yuzlariga nisbatlari

$\left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2 \left(\frac{2}{4}\right)^2$ va $\left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^3$ bo'ladi. Demak, kesimlarning yuzlari quyidagiga teng

quyidagiga teng:

$$400 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2 = 25(sm)^2. \quad 400 \cdot \left(\frac{2}{4}\right)^2 = 100(sm)^2. \quad 400 \cdot \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^2 = 225(sm)^2.$$

Muntazam piramidaning barcha yon qirralari bir-biriga teng; barcha yon yoqlari teng yonli uchburchaklardir.

Muntazam piramida yon yog'ining balandligi bu piramidani apofemasi deyiladi. Agar piramidaning asosi n – burchakdan iborat bo'lsa, u holda bunday piramida n - burchakli piramida deyiladi. Uchburchakli piramida tetraedr deyiladi. Agar tetraedrning barcha qirralari teng bo'lsa, bunday tetraedr muntazam tetraedr deyiladi.

Muntazam piramidaning yon sirti quyidagi formula yordamida hisoblanadi:

$$S_{yon} = P \cdot h,$$

bu yerda P – piramida asosining perimetri, h – apofema.

Piramidaning hajmi quyidagi formula bo'yicha hisoblanadi:

$$V = S \cdot H,$$

bu yerda S – piramida asosining yuzi; H – piramida balandligi.

Piramidani uning asosiga parallel tekislik bilan kesganda ikkita ko'pyoq hosil bo'ladi. Ulardan biri kesik piramida deb ataladi, ikkinchisi piramida bo'lib, u kesik piramidani to'ldiruvchi deyiladi. Kesik piramidani asoslari o'xshash ko'pburchaklardan, yon yoqlari trapetsiyalardan iborat. Kesik piramidaning balandligi deb, oxirlari asoslarida bo'lgan perpendikulyar kesmasiga aytiladi. Agar kesik piramida muntazam piramidaning qismi bo'lsa, muntazam kesik piramida deyiladi.

Muntazam kesik piramidaning yon yoqlari teng yonli trapetsiyalardan iborat. Bu trapetsiyalarning balandligi muntazam kesik piramidaning apofemasi deyiladi. Muntazam kesik piramidaning yon sirti quyidagi formula yordamida hisoblanadi.

$$S_{yon} = (P_1 + P_2) \cdot h,$$

bu yerda $P_1 P_2$ - piramida asoslarining perimetrlari; h – apofema.

Muntazam kesik piramidani hajmi quyidagi formula bo'yicha hisoblanadi:

$$V = (S_1 + S_2) \cdot H$$

bu yerda H – kesik piramida balandligi; $S_1 S_2$ – piramida asoslarining yuzlari.

Agar piramidaning barcha yon qirralari asos tekisligi bilan bir xil burchak tashkil qilsa, yoki qirralari teng bo'lsa, u holda piramidaning balandligi asosiga tashqi chizilgan aylana markaziga tushadi

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati:

1. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
2. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
3. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. World of Scientific news in Science, 1(2), 163-176.
4. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2024). KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 383-390.
5. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG-LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.
6. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
7. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 66-76.
8. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(10), 13-23.
9. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
10. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO 'YICHA TO 'G 'RI MASALALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 375-382.
11. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
12. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). GAMMA FUNKSIYA. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 391-399.
13. Bobokulova, M. (2024). IN MEDICINE FROM ECHOPHRAPHY USE. Development and innovations in science, 3(1), 94-103.

14. Bobokulova, M. (2024). INTERPRETATION OF QUANTUM THEORY AND ITS ROLE IN NATURE. *Models and methods in modern science*, 3(1), 94-109.
15. Bobokulova, M. (2024, January). RADIO WAVE SURGERY. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 56-66).
16. Bobokulova, M. (2024). UNCERTAINTY IN THE HEISENBERG UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 3(2), 80-96.
17. Bobokulova, M. (2024). BLOOD ROTATION OF THE SYSTEM PHYSICIST BASICS. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 3(1), 64-74.
18. Sharipova, M. (2024). IN THE FORM OF AN UNBOUNDED PARALLELEPIPED IN THE FIELD NONLOCAL BORDERLINE CONDITIONAL LINEAR THE REVERSE IS THE CASE. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(1), 105-116.
19. Sharipova, M. (2024). FUNCTIONAL SPACES. IN SHORT REFLECTION PRINCIPLE. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 3(1), 131-142.
20. Sharipova, M. (2024). A IS CORRECT OF THE INTEGRAL TO THE ECONOMY APPLICATIONS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 3(1), 116-125.
21. Sharipova, M. (2024). ASYMMETRY AND KURTOSIS COEFFICIENTS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 3(1), 216-225.
22. Sharipova, M. (2024). TWO MULTIPLE OF THE INTEGRAL APPLICATIONS. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 3(1), 135-140.
23. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 360-365.
24. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 137-141.
25. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 135-138.
26. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(13), 120-128.
27. Axmedova, Z. I. (2024). LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IMKONIYATLARI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 509-516.

28. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 305-309.
29. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 171-177.
30. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 274-280.
31. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(12), 781-787.
32. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.
33. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.
34. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
35. Sharopova, M. (2024). CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 185-191.
36. Sharopova, M. (2024). DSA ERI STANDARD. ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE OF GOST R 34.10-94. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 169-178.
37. Sharopova, M. (2024). COLLECTORS.(OBJECT CONTAINERS). Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 93-101.
38. Sharopova, M. (2024). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE FLOWING INPUT AND RELEASE. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 84-93.
39. Karimov, F. (2022). ANIQ INTEGRALNI TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 14(14).
40. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 95-104.
41. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 117-124.

42. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 108-115.
43. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 122-130.
44. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 208-215.
45. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
46. Просмотр «CALCULATION OF THE THERMODYNAMIC CYCLE OF A VAPOR COMPRESSION HEAT PUMP INSTALLATION WITH A SUBCOOLER FOR HEATING AND HOT WATER SUPPLY.»
47. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). RSA VA EL-GAMAL OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON RAQMLI IMZOLARI. RSA OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDAGI ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZO. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 316-319.
48. Sharopova, M. M. qizi . (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 111-119.
49. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 96-102.
50. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 82-87.
51. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 2(12), 102-107.
52. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
53. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA ULARNI QO 'LLASH USUL VA VOSITALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 481-486.
54. Murodov, O. T. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.

55. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
56. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.
57. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.
58. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.
59. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
60. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
61. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.
62. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. International journal of sciearchers,2(2), 101-103.
63. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.
64. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 102-110.
65. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
66. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 106-113.
67. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 115-121.

68. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 50-56.
69. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 420-424.
70. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 425-429.
71. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 525-532.
72. Sharopova, M. (2023). CLASSES AGAIN APPLY. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 106-111.
73. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING" PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.
74. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.
75. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
76. Quvvatov, B. (2024). DIFFERENTIAL TENGLAMALAR VA AMALIY ECHIMLAR ORQALI MAXSUS MODELLARNI QURISH. Menejment va iqtisodiyotda ijtimoiy muammolarni hal qilish , 3 (1), 108-115.
77. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g', Q. (2023). SUN'IY NERV TIZIMLARIDAN MODELLASHDA FOYDALANISH. Fan va texnologiyaning ko'p tarmoqli jurnali , 3 (5), 269-273.
78. Behruz Ulug'bek og', Q. (2023). TEXNOLOGIYA VA TIBBIYOT: DINAMIK HAMKORLIK. Tadqiqot va ishlanmalar bo'yicha xalqaro multidisipliner jurnali , 10 (11).
79. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA, 1(6), 128-132.
80. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.

81. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
82. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.

